

IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES TODAY

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Annotation: This article discusses the importance of foreign languages today. In addition, the importance of modern methods in teaching foreign languages is analyzed.

Key words: pedagogical technologies, foreign language, educational process.

After our country gained independence, Uzbekistan began to build a democratic life from the first years of independence. The economy was also important. The weight of the implemented reforms increased from year to year. Not only the fundamental reforms, but many changes have taken place in the education system, including in other aspects. In particular, interest in teaching foreign languages has increased and many conditions have been created for young people. The main goal of this is to increase the level of knowledge of young people and increase their interest in foreign languages. As our first president Islam Karimov said, "Currently, the teaching of foreign languages is given great importance in our country. On December 10, 2012, the Presidential Decision on measures to further improve the system of teaching foreign languages" was adopted. This decision further expanded the possibilities of learning foreign languages. Today, the demand for foreign languages is increasing. Currently, a lot of work is being done not only on foreign language teaching, but also on finding new methods of teaching and teaching all subjects and testing them in practice. This is one of the most important problems that must be solved in order to improve the educational process today. If earlier, teaching a foreign language was considered to be the study of this language system, then in the following years, the main goal of teaching was to develop students' foreign language speech. It should be said that these goals in learning a foreign language are not set by themselves or by other people or individuals, but are closely related to the changes in linguistics and psychology and the social development of society. For example: Let's take the audiolingual method. The emergence of this method was influenced by changes in the science of linguistics, i.e. structural flow. Learning a foreign language is a multifaceted education, and in this process, a person experiences complex psychological changes. In particular, the process of comparing the native language with a foreign language occurs. Various methods and technologies of teaching are used in this process. Teaching by comparing the foreign language with the mother

tongue with the help of modern pedagogical technologies gives an effective result. Teaching a foreign language requires knowledge of its methodology. Methodology and technologies are of great importance in the process of learning a foreign language. There are various methods of teaching methodology in the organization of a lesson. Methods widely used in the methodology of foreign language teaching.: method of communicative didactics, method of organization of intercultural dialogue and method of organization of exercises. Foreign languages are becoming an important component of professional education in modern society. Due to the high rate of cooperation with foreign partners among specialists in various fields, their demand for language learning is high. Currently, foreign languages are taught in schools, colleges, lyceums, and higher education institutions. There are innovative types of educational materials for those who want to have different levels of language knowledge. Perfect knowledge of a foreign language and obtaining a certain level also depends on the practical methods and qualifications of teachers. The ability to use information technology and modern teaching methods. helps to quickly understand new materials. By combining different methods, the teacher will be able to solve specific educational programs. In this regard, teachers and students should familiarize themselves with modern methods of teaching foreign languages. As a result, the ability to choose the most effective methods to achieve their goals is formed. Using several methods of teaching and learning can be effective in this regard. Nowadays, innovations are increasing in every field of organization. In short, as a result of using innovative methods in English lessons, students' logical thinking skills develop, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to answer quickly and correctly is formed. Such methods and games instill a passion for knowledge in the student. The student tries to prepare thoroughly for the lessons. This makes the students the subjects of the educational process. The effectiveness of using different tables in the process of teaching a foreign language is also high. Using the tables in the educational process, students can learn a certain grammar rule, for example, making sentences using tenses, placing new words. At a time when the need to learn a foreign language is high, effective use of modern information technologies and innovative educational technologies in the educational process has made this process effective. The effectiveness of innovative educational technologies is when they are used correctly and effectively in the educational process.

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